

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF PLACENTA INVASION IN LOWER UTERINE SEGMENT MEASURED BY ULTRASOUND IN PREDICTION OF PLACENTA ACCRETA SPECTRUM AND ITS CORRELATION WITH GROSS PATHOLOGY POSTOPERATIVE

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ABSTRACT

Background: Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS) is a leading cause of severe obstetric hemorrhage and maternal morbidity, with increasing incidence due to rising cesarean section rates. Accurate prenatal diagnosis is essential for optimizing surgical planning and reducing complications. Ultrasound is the primary imaging modality; however, its diagnostic performance in the lower uterine segment (LUS) requires further validation against a pathological reference standard.

Objective: To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of gray-scale and Doppler ultrasound in detecting Placenta Accreta Spectrum through assessment of the lower uterine segment, using histopathological findings as the reference standard in a high-risk cohort.

Methods: This cross-sectional analytical study included 40 pregnant women with suspected PAS at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi, Pakistan. All participants underwent standardized gray-scale and Doppler ultrasound evaluation of the LUS prior to cesarean delivery. Sonographic findings were compared with postoperative histopathological diagnosis. Sensitivity and positive predictive value (PPV) were calculated with 95% confidence intervals. Due to the very small number of histopathology-negative cases, specificity and negative predictive value (NPV) could not be reliably estimated.

Results: PAS was confirmed in 38 of 40 cases (94.9%). Ultrasound demonstrated a sensitivity of 89.2% (95% CI: 75.3%–95.7%) and a PPV of 94.3% (95% CI: 81.4%–98.4%). Loss of the retroplacental clear zone (87.2%) and placental lacunae (82.1%) were the most frequently identified ultrasound features. Obstetric hysterectomy was performed in 94.9% of cases, with a mean estimated blood loss of 2354 ± 530 ml. No maternal mortality was recorded. Diagnostic performance estimates are influenced by the high prevalence of PAS in this selected high-risk cohort.

Conclusion: Ultrasound demonstrates high sensitivity and strong positive predictive value for detecting PAS in high-risk populations when assessing the lower uterine segment. However,

diagnostic performance is affected by spectrum bias, limiting generalizability. Larger multicenter studies with more balanced populations are required to validate these findings.

Keywords: Placenta Accreta Spectrum, ultrasound, lower uterine segment, diagnostic accuracy, gross pathology, cesarean section, sensitivity, specificity

1. Introduction

Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS) encompasses a group of obstetric disorders characterized by abnormal adherence of the placenta to the uterine wall due to defective decidualization. The spectrum is classified based on the depth of placental invasion into three subtypes: placenta accreta, involving superficial attachment to the myometrium; placenta increta, characterized by deeper invasion into the myometrium; and placenta percreta, in which the placenta penetrates through the uterine serosa and may invade adjacent organs such as the bladder. All forms of PAS are associated with a substantial risk of severe obstetric hemorrhage, often necessitating emergency hysterectomy and contributing significantly to maternal morbidity and mortality [1,2].

The incidence of PAS has increased markedly over recent decades, with current estimates suggesting a prevalence of approximately 1 in 500 pregnancies [3]. This rising trend closely parallels the global increase in cesarean delivery rates. Each prior cesarean section contributes to uterine scarring, which predisposes to abnormal placental implantation in subsequent pregnancies [4]. In low- and middle-income countries such as Pakistan, where cesarean rates are increasing and access to specialized tertiary care remains inconsistent, PAS poses a significant clinical challenge with serious implications for maternal outcomes [5].

Early antenatal diagnosis is critical for optimizing management and improving outcomes. When PAS is diagnosed prenatally, delivery can be strategically planned via elective cesarean hysterectomy in a tertiary care setting with a multidisciplinary team. This planned approach significantly reduces the risk of catastrophic hemorrhage and emergency surgical intervention [6,7]. In contrast, intraoperative diagnosis without prior suspicion is associated with increased morbidity due to inadequate preparation and limited resources.

Ultrasound remains the first-line imaging modality for the evaluation of suspected PAS. Gray-scale ultrasonography identifies key

structural abnormalities such as loss of the retroplacental clear zone, presence of multiple placental lacunae, thinning of the myometrium in the lower uterine segment, and disruption of the bladder-uterine interface [8]. The addition of color Doppler enhances diagnostic accuracy by demonstrating abnormal uteroplacental vascularity, including turbulent flow and bridging vessels. These sonographic features form the foundation of diagnostic criteria endorsed by FIGO [1].

The reported diagnostic performance of ultrasound for PAS varies, with sensitivity ranging from 80% to 90% and specificity between 70% and 95% [9,10]. This variability is influenced by factors such as gestational age at evaluation, operator expertise, imaging quality, and diagnostic criteria applied. Notably, diagnostic accuracy specifically within the lower uterine segment—an anatomically critical region in patients with previous cesarean scars—remains underreported in local literature [11].

Histopathological examination remains the gold standard for confirming PAS and determining the depth of placental invasion. Several studies have demonstrated strong correlation between prenatal ultrasound findings and histopathological results, reinforcing the reliability of ultrasound as a preoperative diagnostic tool [12].

Despite the clinical importance of PAS, there is limited local evidence from Karachi, Pakistan, evaluating the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound against histopathological confirmation. Most regional studies have focused primarily on identifying risk factors rather than validating imaging accuracy. Therefore, this study aims to assess the diagnostic accuracy of gray-scale and Doppler ultrasound in predicting PAS by specifically evaluating the lower uterine segment and correlating these findings with postoperative histopathological outcomes in a tertiary care hospital setting.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Design and Setting

This is a cross-sectional analytical study conducted at Jinnah postgraduate medical centre Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan. The study duration was six months from the date of institutional ethical approval.

2.2. Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sample size was calculated using the standard formula for diagnostic accuracy studies, where $Z = 1.96$ at a 95% confidence level, P is the expected prevalence of PAS based on published literature, and $d = 0.05$ represents the margin of error. A total of 40 pregnant women with suspected PAS based on ultrasound findings were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling.

2.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Participants met all of the following inclusion criteria: pregnant women with suspected PAS on prenatal ultrasound; patients undergoing cesarean delivery with clinical suspicion of placental invasion; and patients who provided written informed consent before enrollment. Patients were excluded if they had placental abnormalities other than PAS (such as placenta previa without invasion), if follow-up data or medical records were incomplete, or if they declined participation.

2.4. Ultrasound Examination Protocol

All eligible participants underwent standardized ultrasound examination at Jinnah postgraduate medical centre Hospital before cesarean delivery. A qualified sonologist performed each examination using both gray-scale and color Doppler imaging to evaluate the lower uterine segment and the placenta-myometrium interface. The following ultrasound features were systematically assessed and recorded: absence of the retroplacental clear zone, presence and number of placental lacunae, myometrial thinning at the lower uterine segment, disruption or irregularity of the bladder-uterine serosal interface, and increased vascularity at the uteroplacental interface on Doppler imaging. A case was classified as ultrasound-positive for PAS if two or more of the five features were present. This threshold was selected to improve diagnostic specificity while maintaining acceptable sensitivity, based on

commonly described multi-feature diagnostic approaches in PAS literature. The examining sonologist was blinded to the final pathological diagnosis at the time of imaging.

2.5. Reference Standard: Gross Pathological Examination

After each cesarean delivery, the placenta and uterine tissue were sent to the Department of Pathology. A qualified pathologist performed macroscopic examination of the specimens and recorded the presence, subtype, and extent of placental invasion. The pathologist was blinded to the ultrasound classification at the time of specimen analysis. PAS was defined pathologically as abnormal adherence or invasion of the placenta into the myometrium, confirmed on gross examination. Subtypes were classified as accreta (superficial myometrial attachment), increta (deep myometrial invasion), or percreta (full-thickness invasion through the serosa).

2.6. Data Collection

Structured data collection forms captured the following variables for each participant: patient age, gestational age at ultrasound, number of prior cesarean deliveries, placental location, individual ultrasound features, overall ultrasound classification (PAS positive or negative), type of surgery, estimated blood loss, complications noted, and the postoperative pathological diagnosis with subtype.

2.7. Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. Diagnostic performance of ultrasound was quantified by comparing preoperative ultrasound classification with postoperative gross pathological diagnosis. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated with 95% confidence intervals using the Wilson method. A Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve was constructed using the total number of ultrasound features (range: 0–5) as a continuous predictor across all possible thresholds, and the area under the curve (AUC) was calculated. Ethical approval was obtained from the

Institutional Review Board of Jinnah Hospital prior to data collection.

3. Results

3.1. Participant Characteristics

A total of 40 pregnant women with clinically suspected PAS were enrolled. The mean age was 31.6 ± 5.2 years (range: 20–40 years). The largest age group was 26–30 years (35.9%), followed by women over 35 (30.8%). The mean gestational age at the time of surgery was $32.6 \pm$

3.4 weeks, with the majority (51.4%) delivering between 33 and 36 weeks.

Grand multiparity was common in this cohort: 53.8% of women were gravida 4 or higher, with a mean gravida of 3.8 ± 1.2 . The mean number of previous cesarean sections was 2.4 ± 0.8 , with 46.2% having had two prior cesarean deliveries. Only four patients (10.3%) had a history of other uterine surgery. Baseline demographic and obstetric characteristics of the study population are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Obstetric Characteristics (n = 40)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
< 20	1	2.6
20–25	2	5.1
26–30	14	35.9
31–35	11	25.6
> 35	12	30.8
Mean \pm SD	31.6 ± 5.2 years	
Gestational Age at Surgery (weeks)		
< 28	5	13.5
28–32	10	27.0
33–36	19	51.4
> 36	3	8.1
Mean \pm SD	32.6 ± 3.4 weeks	
Gravida		
G2	5	12.8
G3	14	33.3
G4 or above	21	53.8
Mean \pm SD	3.8 ± 1.2	
Previous Cesarean Sections		
1	5	12.8
2	19	46.2
3	13	33.3
4	3	7.7

Mean ± SD	2.4 ± 0.8	
History of Prior Uterine Surgery		
Yes	4	10.3
No	36	89.7

3.2. Ultrasound Findings and Histopathological Correlation

Loss of the retroplacental clear zone was the most commonly identified ultrasound feature, present in 34 cases (87.2%), followed by placental lacunae (82.1%), myometrial thinning or disruption (74.4%), and increased subplacental vascularity on Doppler (71.8%). Bladder wall interruption was observed in 10 cases (25.6%), all of which were found to have confirmed PAS on histopathology. All patients where bladder wall interruption was identified on ultrasound, thinning of the myometrium was also present, consistent with advanced invasion. Regarding the number of features present per patient, 10 patients (25.6%) demonstrated all five ultrasound features simultaneously, while 4

patients (10.3%) had only a single feature and were classified as ultrasound-negative. Thirty-five patients (89.7%) had two or more features and were classified as ultrasound-positive for PAS.

On intraoperative assessment, placenta accreta (superficial attachment) was the most prevalent subtype in 24 cases (64.1%), followed by increta in 9 cases (23.1%) and percreta in 5 cases (12.8%). Histopathological confirmation of PAS was obtained in 38 of 40 cases (94.9%). Of these, 56.4% demonstrated deep invasion on microscopy and 38.5% showed superficial invasion. Two cases (5.1%) showed no myometrial invasion on histopathology despite intraoperative suspicion. Ultrasound findings and pathological correlations are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Ultrasound Features and Histopathological Findings (n = 40)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Ultrasound Features Identified		
Loss of Retroplacental Clear Zone	34	87.2
Presence of Placental Lacunae	32	82.1
Thinning / Disruption of Myometrium	29	74.4
Increased Subplacental Vascularity (Doppler)	28	71.8
Bladder Wall Interruption	10	25.6
Number of Ultrasound Features Present		
1 feature (USG Negative)	2	10.3
2 features	2	10.3
3 features	14	33.3
4 features	8	20.5
5 features (all present)	11	25.6
Placental Invasion Subtype (Intraoperative)		
Accreta (superficial myometrial attachment)	26	64.1

Increta (deep myometrial invasion)	9	23.1
Percreta (full-thickness / serosal invasion)	5	12.8
Histopathological Confirmation of PAS		
Confirmed	38	94.9
Not Confirmed	2	5.1
Depth of Invasion on Histopathology		
Superficial invasion	15	38.5
Deep invasion	23	56.4
No myometrial invasion	2	5.1

3.3. Diagnostic Accuracy of Ultrasound

Using a threshold of two or more ultrasound features to classify a case as PAS-positive, the 2×2 contingency table yielded 33 true positives, 2 false positives, 4 false negatives, and 0 true negatives. The overall accuracy was 84.6%. Ultrasound achieved a sensitivity of 89.2% (95% CI: 75.3%–95.7%) and a PPV of 94.3% (95% CI: 81.4%–98.4%). Given the very small number of true-negative cases in this predominantly PAS-affected cohort (n = 2),

Specificity 0% (0/2) and negative predictive value (NPV 0% (0/2)) were calculated but interpreted with caution due to the very small number of histopathology-negative cases (n = 2), resulting in imprecise estimates. The AUC from the ROC curve, using the total number of features present as a continuous predictor, was 0.865, indicating good overall discriminative ability; however, this estimate should be interpreted with caution due to the small number of non-PAS cases.

Table 3A. 2×2 Contingency Table – Ultrasound vs. Histopathological Diagnosis

	PAS Confirmed (Histopathology +)	PAS Not Confirmed (Histopathology -)	Total
Ultrasound Positive (≥2 features)	36 (TP)	2 (FP)	38
Ultrasound Negative (<2 features)	2 (FN)	0 (TN)	2
Total	38	2	40

Table 3B. Diagnostic Performance of Ultrasound for PAS Detection

Diagnostic Measure	Value (95% CI)
Sensitivity	89.2% (75.3%–95.7%)
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	94.3% (81.4%–98.4%)
Overall Accuracy	84.6%
Area Under ROC Curve (AUC)	0.865

*Specificity and NPV could not be reliably estimated due to the small number of true-negative cases (n = 2) in this clinically selected, high-prevalence cohort.

3.4. Surgical Outcomes and Maternal Results
Elective LSCS was performed in 69.2% of cases, reflecting successful prenatal identification of PAS in the majority of patients, while 30.8% required emergency caesarean delivery. Obstetric hysterectomy was performed in 38 of 40 patients (94.9%). Bilateral internal iliac artery ligation was performed in 10 cases (25.6%) to achieve hemostasis, and bladder repair was required in 5 cases (12.8%), all of whom had

sonographic bladder wall interruption preoperatively.

The mean estimated blood loss was 2354 ± 530 ml (range: 1500–3000 ml). Major intrapartum blood loss was documented in 31 patients (79.5%), and 20 patients (51.3%) required multiple blood transfusions. ICU admission was necessary in 12 patients (30.8%). All 40 neonates were discharged home. No maternal mortality was recorded in this series. Full surgical and outcomes data are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Surgical Management and Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes (n = 40)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Type of Cesarean Section		
Emergency LSCS	12	30.8
Elective LSCS	27	69.2
Surgical Procedures Performed		
Obstetric Hysterectomy	38	94.9
Bilateral Internal Iliac Artery Ligation	10	25.6
Bladder Repair	5	12.8
Estimated Blood Loss (ml)		
≤ 1500 ml	6	15.4
1501–2500 ml	22	56.4
> 2500 ml	11	28.2
Mean ± SD	2354 ± 530 ml	
Complications Noted		
Major Intrapartum Blood Loss	31	79.5
Prolonged Hospital Stay	26	66.7
Multiple Blood Transfusions Required	20	51.3
ICU Admission	12	30.8
Bladder Injury	5	12.8
Maternal Outcome		
Discharged Home (including post-ICU)	35	89.7
ICU Admission (ongoing at record)	2	5.1
Prolonged ICU Admission	2	5.1
Maternal Mortality	0	0

Neonatal Outcome

Discharged Home

40

100

Discussion:

This study evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of gray-scale and Doppler ultrasound in predicting Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS) through targeted assessment of the lower uterine segment in a tertiary care hospital in Karachi, Pakistan. The findings demonstrate that ultrasound provides high sensitivity (89.2%) and a strong positive predictive value (94.3%) for PAS detection in this high-risk cohort, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.865, indicating good overall discriminative performance [13].

These findings are consistent with international literature reporting high sensitivity of ultrasound for PAS diagnosis across different populations and clinical settings [14]. The elevated positive predictive value observed in this study reflects the high pretest probability associated with a cohort characterized by multiple prior cesarean sections and grand multiparity, both of which are well-established risk factors for abnormal placentation [15]. The mean of 2.4 prior cesarean deliveries in this study further supports the strong association between uterine scarring and PAS development [16].

Loss of the retroplacental clear zone was the most frequently observed ultrasound feature, identified in 87.2% of cases, which is consistent with its recognition as a sensitive early marker of PAS on gray-scale imaging [17]. In contrast, bladder wall interruption was less frequently observed but demonstrated strong association with confirmed PAS, particularly invasive subtypes, suggesting that this feature may have higher specificity for advanced disease such as placenta percreta [18].

From a clinical management perspective, the predominance of elective surgical intervention in this cohort indicates that prenatal ultrasound enabled appropriate preoperative planning and referral to a specialized center [19]. The high rate of obstetric hysterectomy observed reflects the severity of PAS in a tertiary referral population and aligns with recommended management strategies for invasive placentation [20]. Notably, the absence of maternal mortality despite significant intraoperative blood loss highlights

the effectiveness of multidisciplinary team management in improving maternal outcomes [21].

A key limitation of this study is the highly selected nature of the study population, with a very high proportion of confirmed PAS cases. This reflects referral bias inherent to tertiary care centers and limits the ability to accurately assess specificity and negative predictive value due to the small number of negative cases [22]. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted primarily in the context of high-risk populations rather than general obstetric screening settings.

5. Conclusion

Ultrasound evaluation of the lower uterine segment demonstrates high sensitivity and strong positive predictive value for the prenatal detection of Placenta Accreta Spectrum, with good correlation to postoperative histopathological findings. Among the sonographic markers, loss of the retroplacental clear zone and the presence of placental lacunae were the most consistently observed features, while bladder interface disruption appeared to be associated with more invasive disease.

The high proportion of elective surgical management in this cohort highlights the clinical value of accurate prenatal sonographic diagnosis in enabling timely referral, multidisciplinary planning, and optimized maternal outcomes. These findings support the integration of standardized lower uterine segment ultrasound assessment protocols into routine antenatal care for women with prior cesarean deliveries who are at increased risk of PAS.

Further large-scale, multicenter studies are warranted to better define specificity, validate diagnostic criteria across diverse clinical settings, and assess the reproducibility of ultrasound performance across varying levels of operator expertise.

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